

Glassy Poly(methacrylate) Terpolymers with Covalently Attached Emitters and Sensitizers for Low-Power Light Upconversion

Soo Hyon Lee, David C. Thévenaz, Christoph Weder*, and Yoan C. Simon*

Adolphe Merkle Institute, University of Fribourg, Chemin des Verdiers 4, CH-1700 Fribourg, Switzerland

Correspondence to: Christoph Weder (E-mail: christoph.weder@unifr.ch), Yoan Simon (E-mail: yoan.simon@unifr.ch)

((Additional Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.))

ABSTRACT

Low-power light upconversion by triplet–triplet annihilation (TTA-UC) was only recently demonstrated in glassy polymers and the upconversion efficiency in these materials is typically much lower than in solution. As aggregation of the chromophores was thought to be the culprit, we here report the covalent tethering of a suitable chromophore pair to a polymeric backbone. The new materials were based on the sensitizer-bearing monomer palladium meso-phenoxy-tris(heptyl)porphyrin-ethylmethacrylate (PdmPH3PMA), which was copolymerized with a diphenylanthracene (DPA) emitter and methyl methacrylate (MMA) as an optically inert co-monomer. The DPA content was kept rather constant at 30-37 wt%, while the PdmPH3PMA content was varied between 0.73-0.012 wt%. To explore additional compositions, blends of a high-porphyrin-content terpolymer with a DPAMA-MMA copolymer were also prepared. All of the materials studied were processed into thin films by solution-casting and displayed blue TTA-UC emission. The UC emission intensity was found to strongly depend on the composition and the underlying effects were investigated through a systematic study.

KEYWORDS: Light upconversion, sensitization, porphyrin, triplet-triplet annihilation, chromophore attachment

INTRODUCTION

Low-power upconversion of non-coherent light by triplet-triplet annihilation (TTA-UC) is a useful non-linear optical process that permits to change the wavelength of light to higher energy.¹⁻³ Observed in solution already in the 1960's,^{4,5} this phenomenon was shown to occur in solid mixtures of sensitizers in conjugated polymeric systems only some ten years ago,^{6,7} before it was demonstrated in elastomeric polymers comprising green-to-blue UC chromophores.⁸ In the latter studies, small amounts of palladium octaethylporphyrin

(PdOEP) and 9,10-diphenylanthracene (DPA), a well-known TTA-UC sensitizer/emitter pair, were incorporated into a ethyleneoxide/epichlorohydrin copolymer matrix by solution-casting.^{8,9} It was shown that the upconverted fluorescence intensity was highly dependent on the temperature and decreased dramatically below the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the polymer.^{10,11} This result suggested that translational and rotational mobility of the chromophores is essential for efficient upconversion in solid materials with low chromophore content,^{12,13} as the influence on the various energy transfer steps that are

involved in the TTA-UC process is significant.⁹ It was later hypothesized that an increase of the UC chromophore concentrations in the matrix could change this situation by way of enabling energy transfer on account of small intermolecular distances and, thus, increase the efficiency of TTA-UC process in the solid state.^{25,26} Therefore, glassy TTA-UC blends with rather high content of chromophores were explored.¹⁴⁻¹⁸ However, incorporating high concentrations of chromophores in rubbery materials by way of blending is challenging due to phase separation.¹⁹ Monguzzi *et al.* reported TTA-UC in glassy ($T_g = 67$ °C) cellulose acetate films, which were produced by drop-casting a solution containing the polymer and the dyes (palladium(II) meso-tetraphenyltetra-benzoporphyrin and 9,10-bis(phenylethynyl)anthracene in concentrations of 0.2% wt% or less (relative to the polymer) onto a hot glass substrate.^{14,15} We subsequently reported the incorporation of the PdOEP-DPA UC chromophore pair into an amorphous poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) matrix by melt-processing. This strategy permitted to considerably increase the DPA content by kinetically trapping up to 20 wt% of the sensitizer using rapid cooling of homogeneous melts.²⁰ To further increase the emitter content, two avenues were explored by our group, the use of a molecular-glass-forming DPA derivatives²¹ and the covalent tethering of DPA derivatives to polymers.²² Surprisingly, the investigation of a series of polymers based on the latter framework pointed to the fact that maximizing the emitter content does not necessarily equate to optimal upconversion intensity. For instance, in the case of polymer-tethered emitters, the maximum upconversion intensity increased with the emitter content up to a DPA content of *ca.* 35 wt%, but dropped markedly when the DPA content was further increased. In addition, all glassy materials with high DPA content studied by us thus far, display a decreasing UC emission intensity with increasing porphyrin content.^{20,22} Several hypotheses have been put forth to explain this behavior, including limited triplet diffusion, re-

absorption, excimer formation and porphyrin aggregation, which was spectroscopically confirmed in the case of Pt octaethyl porphyrin compounds.²¹⁻²³

The present study sought to explore whether the solubility of the sensitizer molecules and electronic relaxation pathways involving aggregates of the sensitizer molecules are indeed to blame. While several groups have explored the connection of emitter and sensitizer units in polymers,^{19,24-27} little has been done in the context of understanding how it impacted thick polymeric films. We therefore prepared and studied glassy terpolymers in which both the sensitizer and the emitter are covalently connected to a polymeric backbone as pendant groups. This design prevents phase separation effects and permits the variation of the chromophore concentrations over a large compositional range. Thus, we synthesized the new sensitizer-bearing monomer palladium meso-phenoxy-tris(heptyl)porphyrin-ethyl-methacrylate (PdmPH₃PMA) and copolymerized the latter with a known DPA-bearing methacrylate (DPAMA)²² and methyl methacrylate (MMA) as an optically inert comonomer. The concentration of the sensitizer was systematically varied and the optical properties were correlated with the composition.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and methods. All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and were used without any further purification, except for 2,2'-azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN), which was purified by recrystallization from methanol prior to use. The copolymer poly(DPAMA-*co*-MMA) was produced following the procedure described for **polymer 3** in Ref. 22. All purification steps were performed by flash column chromatography (FCC) using a Biotage® IsoleraOne™. Molecular weights were determined versus poly(styrene) standards by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) equipped with PSS SECcurity injector, two Polymer Laboratories PSS SDV linear M columns

(dimension 8 x 300 mm, particle size 5 μm) along with Wyatt Technology Corp. (Optilab REX interferometric refractometer, miniDawn TREOS laser photometer) and Agilent Technologies instrumentation (series 1200 HPLC) and Wyatt Technology software (ASTRA) were used for the GPC analysis. Mass spectra were acquired by the Analytical Services of the Chemistry Department at the University of Fribourg, Switzerland. ^1H (360 MHz) and ^{13}C (75 MHz) NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Advance III spectrometer in CD_2Cl_2 (Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc.).

21H,23H-5-(2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-ethanol)-

10,15,20-tris (heptyl)porphyrin, (mPH₃P). In a 3 L round bottom flask, pyrrole (40 mmol, 2.68 g, 4 equiv.), hydroxyethylbenzaldehyde (10 mmol, 1.66 g, 1 equiv.) and octanal (30 mmol, 3.846 g, 3 eq.) were dissolved in dichloromethane (DCM, 2 L). Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, 1.5 mL, 10^{-2} M) was added drop-wise to the reaction mixture at r.t. and the mixture was subsequently stirred for 2.5 h. After addition of 2,3-Dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone (5 g) to quench the reaction, the mixture was stirred overnight. Et_3N (5 mL) was finally added at r.t. to neutralize the TFA. The crude solution was filtered through AlO_3 , before the volume was reduced in vacuo and the product was purified by FCC with hexane:EtOAc = 3:2, R_f = 0.5. The title compound was obtained as a dark brown solid with a yield of 12%. ^1H NMR (360 MHz, CD_2Cl_2 , δ): 9.47-9.33 ppm (m, 2H+4H, Pyrrole+benzyl), 8.76 (d, 2H), 7.93 (d, 2H), 7.12 (d, 2H), 4.87 (m, 6H), 2.45 (m, 6H), 1.78 (m, 6H), 1.49 (m, 6H), 1.42-1.36 (m, 12H), 1.04 (s, 9H), -2.87 (s, 2H, NH) ; ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CD_2Cl_2 , δ): 160.3 ppm, 137, 131.8, 120.8, 119.4, 114.3, 63.1, 38.9, 36.6, 33.6, 32.2, 31.1, 24.3, 16.1; MALDI-MS (m/z): 740.51 (calculated: 740.50).

21H,23H-5-(2-(4-phenoxy)ethylmethacrylate)-

10,15,20-tris(heptyl)porphyrin, (mPH₃PMA). In a 100 mL round-bottom-flask, mPH₃P (0.2 mmol, 150 mg, 1 eq.), 4-dimethylaminopyridine (0.01 mmol, 1.2 mg), and Et_3N (0.61 mmol, 48.19 mg, 3 eq.) were dissolved in dry THF (50 mL).

Methacrylic anhydride (0.61 mmol, 94 mg, 3 eq.) was added drop-wise to the reaction mixture at 0 °C, and the mixture was stirred overnight at r.t. After evaporation of solvent, the crude product was purified by FCC with hexane:EtOAc = 3:1, R_f = 0.67. The title compound was obtained as a dark purple solid with a yield of 45%. ^1H NMR (360 MHz, CD_2Cl_2 , δ): 9.47-9.41 ppm (m, 2H+4H), 8.86-8.85 (d, 2H), 8.04-8.01 (d, 2H, Pyrrole), 7.22-7.20 (d, 2H), 6.34 (s, 1H), 5.79 (s, 1H), 4.87 (m, 6H), 4.68 (t, 2H), 4.41 (t, 2H), 2.56 (m, 6H), 2.09 (m, 3H), 1.78 (m, 6H), 1.54 (m, 6H), 1.42-1.36 (m, 12H), 1.04 (s, 9H), -2.71 (s, 2H, NH) ; ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CD_2Cl_2 , δ): 168.0 (OCHO) ppm, 159.1, 137.2, 136.2, 136.1, 126.5, 120.2, 119.9, 118.5, 113.5, 67.1, 65.5, 64.1, 39.7, 32.8, 31.4, 31.3, 30.3, 23.6, 19.0, 14.8; MALDI-MS (m/z): 809.13 (calculated: 808.53).

Palladium(II)-5-(2-(4-phenoxy)ethylmethacrylate)-10,15,20-

tris(heptyl)porphyrin, (PdmPH₃PMA). In a 100-mL round-bottom-flask, mPH₃PMA (0.135 mmol, 100 mg, 1 eq.) and $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ (0.67 mmol, 150 mg, 5 eq.) were dissolved in a mixture of dichloromethane (65 mL) and methanol (16 mL) and the solution mixture was stirred over night at r.t. under argon atmosphere. The solvent was evaporated, and the crude product was purified by FCC in DCM, R_f = 0.36. The title compound was obtained as a red solid with a yield of 89%. MALDI-MS (m/z): 912.40 (calculated: 912.42).

General procedure for the synthesis of poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MMA-*stat*-PdmPH₃PMA) by free radical polymerization. Terpolymer A1. In a 5 mL Schlenk tube under argon, MMA (2.19 mmol, 220 mg), DPAMA (0.44 mmol, 200 mg), PdmPH₃PMA (0.0034 mmol, 3 mg) and AIBN (0.0067 mmol, 1.08 mg) were dissolved in dry toluene (2 mL). After degassing the mixture under argon for 30 min in an ice bath, the mixture was placed in a pre-heated oil bath at 70 °C and the reaction was allowed to proceed at this temperature for 5 h. The content of the tube was subsequently precipitated drop-wise into 200 mL of r.t. methanol. The solid polymer

was collected after centrifugation at 3500 rpm for 15 min with a yield of 55%. The composition of the copolymers was determined by ^1H NMR spectra by comparing the integrations of the benzylic protons of DPAMA at $\delta = 4.0$ ppm with the ester protons of both DPAMA and MMA at $\delta = 3.5$ ppm (Figure S7 through S11).

General preparation of films by solution-casting.

Terpolymer film (Series A). Terpolymer A1 (30 mg) was dissolved in THF (0.5 mL). The resulting viscous solution was drop-cast on a glass slide, and then placed in a vacuum oven at 50 °C overnight.

Blend Film (Series B). Terpolymer A1 (20 mg) was dissolved with DPAMA copolymer 3 (10 mg) in THF (0.5 mL). The resulting solution was drop-cast in the same manner as the method for Series A). The thickness of films of all series was measured about 80 μm using Caliper pro-max.

Optical experiments. Optical absorption spectra were recorded with a Shimadzu UV-2401PC UV-vis spectrophotometer. The fluorescence spectra of DPA in terpolymer materials were measured in steady-state on a Photon Technology International (PTI) C720 spectrophotometer equipped with a Hamamatsu R928P photomultiplier. Upconverted fluorescence was produced by exciting the upconverting samples with a green Nd:YAG laser (at 532 nm with 208 mW/cm^2 as power density) and recording the emission with the spectrophotometer described above. Power densities were varied using reflective power density filters (Thorlabs) and measured with an optical power meter (Thorlabs PM100USB with photodiode power sensor S120VC).

Thermal studies. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were performed on a Mettler-Toledo TGA STAR instrument by heating the samples from 25 °C to 500 °C under N_2 . Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments were performed

on Mettler-Toledo STAR DSC instrument by heating the samples from 25 °C to 200 °C, cooling from 200 °C to 0 °C, and heating again to 250 °C under N_2 atmosphere. All experiments were conducted with heating or cooling rates of 10 °C/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Porphyrin-Based Monomer Synthesis.

For the synthesis of the sensitizer-bearing monomer, Rothmund's method²⁸ was utilized. This reaction is based on the condensation of a pyrrole and an aldehyde under dilute conditions. To attain monofunctional porphyrins, two different functional aldehydes were employed with a 3:1 stoichiometric ratio to provide a single functional group at the meso-position. The selection of aldehydes and pyrrole was based on two guiding principles: i) the photophysical properties of the newly synthesized porphyrin should be akin to PdOEP, and ii) a simple post-functionalization with monomeric function should permit to attach a polymerizable handle. Unfortunately, the spectroscopic properties of non-symmetrically functionalized porphyrins have only been sparsely investigated in the literature.²⁹⁻³² The porphyrin-monomer structure was therefore selected by inference from the energy levels of symmetrically functionalized porphyrins²⁹ and those of meso-phenyl-octaethylporphyrin.^{2,33,34} To introduce a reactive group at the meso-position, 4-(2-hydroxyethoxy)benzaldehyde was chosen. Octanal was utilized for the three other meso-positions, based on the assumption that the long-alkyl chains surrounding the porphyrin core would enhance solubility and limit porphyrin aggregation. The meso-functionalized porphyrin, 21H,23H-5-(2-(4-phenoxy)-ethanol)-10,15,20-tris(heptyl)porphyrin, (mPH₃P) was successfully prepared upon condensation of the aforementioned aldehydes and pyrrole (Scheme 1). The yield of the targeted porphyrin was expectedly low (4-12 %), on the account of the statistical nature of the reaction, which also affords the tetra-heptyl porphyrin, as well as porphyrins with two, three, and four

hydroxyethylphenyl groups. Reaction of mPH₃P with methacrylic anhydride readily afforded the porphyrin-based methacrylic monomer mPH₃PMA. Given the presence of the methacrylic group, which might polymerize at higher temperatures, it was important to conduct the subsequent metallation of the porphyrin under mild conditions. This was possible at room temperature by employing Buchler's method using palladium acetate (Pd(OAc)₂).³⁵ Despite the non-planarity of the non-symmetric porphyrin,³⁶ the metallated porphyrin monomer PdmPH₃PMA was isolated in a remarkably high yield of 89%.

Gratifyingly, the metal insertion promoted the expected changes to the absorption spectra. While the spectrum of the free-base porphyrin mPH₃PMA features four to five Q bands spread between 450-750 nm, the absorption spectrum of PdmPH₃PMA in toluene shows a Soret band at 420 nm and two Q bands at 530 (β) and 560 nm (α) (Figure 1, Supporting Figures S5, S6). The relative intensities of the α and β Q-bands provide some information about the metal-porphyrin conformation. For the stable planar-shaped PdOEP, the absorbance of the α band (543 nm) is five times higher than that of the β band (530 nm, Supporting Figure S6). Interestingly, the β band (530 nm) of PdmPH₃PMA is stronger than its α band (560 nm, Figure S5 S6). This inverse relationship of the Q bands is indicative of a ruffled or saddle conformation, which can be accounted for by the functionalization at the meso-position and the non-symmetrical structure.³⁷ Upon excitation of the β band with a laser at 532 nm (2.5 mW, 208 mW/cm²), PdmPH₃PMA shows red phosphorescence with a maximum at 615 nm (Figure 1). To assess the suitability of the new sensitizer for upconversion in combination with DPAMA, *i.e.*, the DPA-methacrylate monomer described in our previous work,²² a degassed toluene solution comprising 0.5 wt% of DPAMA and 0.05 wt% of PdmPH₃PMA was prepared and the upconverted fluorescence was monitored upon excitation with a 532 nm Nd:YAG laser (Figure 1). The solution displayed

the expected delayed fluorescence, although it is noted that the high-energy part of the emission was partly reabsorbed by the sensitizer, because the Soret band of PdmPH₃PMA (420 nm) overlaps significantly with the fluorescence of DPAMA (390 - 510 nm, Figure 1, Supporting Figure S6).

Free-Radical Copolymerization of the UC Dye Pair.

To investigate the influence of the palladium (II)-21H,23H-5-(2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-ethanol)-10,15,20-tris (heptyl)porphyrin PdmPH₃P content on the TTA-UC process in glassy materials with covalently attached dyes, two strategies were adopted in this work. Copolymers referred to as **Series A** were prepared by copolymerizing DPAMA, MMA, and PdmPH₃PMA in various ratios. **Series B** was prepared by blending a poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MMA-*stat*-PdmPH₃PMA) terpolymer with fixed composition (**A1**, Table 1, and Scheme 2) with a poly(DPAMA-*co*-MMA) copolymer. In both cases, a fixed DPA content of 37 wt% was targeted, as this concentration afforded the highest upconversion efficiency in previously studied blends of poly(DPAMA-*co*-MMA) with PdOEP.²²

Series A was prepared by conventional free radical polymerization of DPAMA, PdmPH₃PMA, and MMA, using AIBN as an initiator. The content of PdmPH₃PMA was systematically varied, while a constant DPA content of 37 wt% was targeted. The polymerization was terminated at yields between 32 and 66 %. NMR spectroscopy shows a good agreement between the feed ratios of DPAMA and MMA and the copolymer composition (Figures S7-S11, Table 1). The incorporation of PdmPH₃PMA was quantified by UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy. The spectra of the terpolymers (Figure S25) all exhibit the diagnostic absorption bands of PdmPH₃PMA (Figure S5) and using the extinction coefficient of PdmPH₃PMA (calculated with the extinction coefficient of the β-Q band, $\epsilon = 29\,560$ L/mol/cm at 530 nm), the concentration of the sensitizer in the

copolymers was determined to range from 0.012 to 0.73 wt%. We note that in all cases, the concentration of the sensitizer in the copolymer is about half of that in the monomer feed (Table 1), which indicates that the reactivity of PdmPH₃PMA is a bit sluggish, possibly due to the sterically demanding nature of the porphyrin. It is important to point out that the DPA and DPAMA weight ratios are different as DPAMA also contains some optically inactive methacrylate portion.

The number-average molecular weight, M_n , of the terpolymers in **Series A** was determined by size exclusion chromatography and ranged from 120 000 to 145 000 g/mol, except for **A3**, which had a M_n of 450 000 g/mol. The molar-mass dispersity (\bar{D}) ranged between from 1.7 to 2.7, which is typical for the free-radical polymerization conditions utilized.

The thermal behavior of the terpolymers of **Series A** was characterized by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The TGA trace of terpolymer A1 (with the max PdmPH₃P content, 0.73 wt%) showed a 2% weight loss at 185 °C and displays a similar thermal stability as the copolymer poly(DPAMA-co-MMA) reported previously (Figure S17).²² The first and second heating curves of all DSC thermograms exclusively show a glass transition around *ca.* 140 °C (Figure S18 - S22) and are void of signals associated with other thermal transitions, such as melting or crystallization events. Thus, the DSC data indicate that the materials were completely amorphous, which is consistent with their highly transparent nature, the expected stereochemistry, and the fact that the corresponding poly(DPAMA-co-MMA) with similar DPAMA and MMA content (without PdmPH₃PMA) was also amorphous.²²

Upconversion with Polymers of Terpolymer Series A.

The absorption spectra of the polymers of series **A** in solution appear to be linear combinations of the respective absorption

spectra of the emitter/sensitizer pair (Figure S26). Given the high emitter/sensitizer ratios, the spectra are of course dominated by the DPA absorption. However, the Soret band of the porphyrin can still be distinguished as a shoulder at 420 nm, particularly in the case of polymer **A1**. By contrast, the Q bands are almost undetectable for all polymers in toluene solutions at a concentration of 0.12 mg/mL. Bright blue fluorescence was observed when solutions of polymers of **Series A** were excited at 375 nm, *i.e.* at a wavelength at which the absorption is dominated by the DPA moiety. The spectral shape of the fluorescence of the polymers in solution was found to be largely independent of the porphyrin content (Figure 2). Upon excitation at 532 nm with a Nd:YAG laser (2.5 mW, 208 mW/cm²), a solution of terpolymer **A1** in degassed toluene was exemplarily shown to exhibit upconverted emission between 425-500 nm, which is similar to that observed for a solution of the monomers DPAMA and PdmPH₃PMA (Figure 2). However, in the case of the monomer mixture, the emission at 413 nm was almost entirely suppressed, whereas it was clearly present for terpolymer **A1**. Moreover, a slight blue-shift was observed for the terpolymer emission, which is probably due to reduced porphyrin reabsorption. Since the fluorescence of DPA (390-500 nm) partly overlapped with the Soret band of PdmPH₃P (420 nm), the upconverted emission in its Soret band region was indeed reabsorbed by the sensitizer as was previously noticed for the monomer mixture (Figure 1).

Films of the terpolymers **A1-A5** with a thickness of about 80 μm were prepared by solution-casting from THF and subsequent drying *in vacuo*. At all sensitizer concentrations the films remained completely transparent, although they became increasingly red with increasing content (Figure 3(a)).

The absorption spectra of films of **Series A** show saturation below 430 nm, due to the combined absorption of DPA and PdmPH₃P (Figure 4(a)). The films are highly transmissive above 450 nm,

except for the Q bands of PdmPH₃P centered at 530 and 560 nm, whose intensity increases with the sensitizer content in a linear manner (Figure S28).

All solid samples show blue fluorescence upon excitation at 375 nm, *i.e.*, at a wavelength where the incident light is primarily absorbed by the DPA emitter moieties. The fluorescence maximum is red-shifted by *ca.* 10 nm in comparison to the corresponding solution, as shown exemplarily for copolymer **A1** in Figure 2. Interestingly, the intensity of the DPA fluorescence *decreased* with increasing sensitizer content; this is clearly visible from a picture that shows samples of **Series A** under excitation with the light of a UV lamp operated at 365 nm (Figure 3b). Since (i) all materials of the series have virtually the same DPA content (30-37 wt%); (ii) the films made had similar thickness (about 80 μm); and (iii) PdmPH₃P does not significantly absorb at the excitation wavelength and should only re-absorb a small portion of the DPA emission (Figure 1 and 2), it appears that the DPA emission is in fact quenched by the presence of PdmPH₃P. This effect was quantitatively investigated by determining the emission intensity of samples of **Series A** upon excitation at 375 nm. Indeed, the fluorescence intensity decreased considerably with increasing PdmPH₃P content (Figure 4(b) and S27), confirming the role of PdmPH₃P as a quencher for DPA fluorescence. Given the above-discussed relative positions of DPA and PdmPH₃P absorption and emission bands, we speculate that this quenching is due to the formation of exciplexes.²²

Gratifyingly, films of terpolymers **A1-A5** all exhibited upconverted blue emission upon excitation at 532 nm with a Nd:YAG green laser (2.5 mW, 208 mW/cm², Figure 5 and Figure 6). While the upconverted emission spectrum matches the shape of the fluorescence spectrum (Figure 2) a red-shift of *ca.* 10 nm was observed.

Very much like the normal fluorescence caused upon direct excitation of the DPA motifs (*vide supra*) the upconverted fluorescence intensity decreased with increasing PdmPH₃P content. This trend was already observed in previously studied PMMA blends,²⁰ as well as in copolymer blends.²² The data shown here suggest that exciplex formation appears to be the culprit.

Besides the upconverted emission, all films of **Series A** surprisingly exhibited very significant phosphorescence. It is important to point out that we observed a significant variation between samples but, apart from polymer **A2** which does not fit the trend, there was a general tendency of increased upconverted emission intensity and decreased phosphorescence with decreasing porphyrin content (Figure 5). The phosphorescence was split into two distinct emission bands at 616 nm (as observed for the phosphorescence of PdmPH₃PMA in solution) and 724 nm. Interestingly, despite an apparent red-shift, a similar phosphorescence pattern could be observed on the emission spectrum of crystalline PdmPH₃PMA upon excitation at 532 nm (Figure S29). We surmise that at high concentration, the PdmPH₃P molecules tend to form emissive stacks, whose phosphorescence is red-shifted compared to that of the corresponding single molecules in solution. Together, these results suggest that, despite the covalent tethering to the polymer backbone, the sensitizer is involved in additional energy transfer processes that result in significant energy losses. This result is again consistent with the aforementioned excimer formation.

Aside from the influence of the sensitizer concentration, the dependence of the UC emission intensity of terpolymer **A1** on the excitation power was investigated by varying the power density of the incident light from 20 to 208 mW/cm² using a set of neutral density filters (Figure 7(a)). The data thus acquired were plotted in a double-logarithmic plot and the analysis shows that the data can be fitted to a linear function with a slope of 1.45 (Figure 7(b)),

which is indicative of a pseudo-linear relationship. Given the multitude of undesired relaxation processes for the excited states, such as exciplex formation, reabsorption and porphyrin aggregation, it is somewhat surprising to find a non-quadratic behavior. However, this pseudo-linear trend may indicate that these detrimental losses mostly affect alternate energy transfers and not the TTA step *per se*.

Upconversion with Polymers of Series B.

The materials in **Series B** were prepared by blending the poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MMA-*stat*-PdmPH₃PMA) terpolymer **A1** (Table 1, and Scheme 2) with poly(DPAMA-*co*-MMA) ($M_n = 110\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$, $\bar{D} = 1.9$).²² This approach permitted rapid access to other compositions in which the sensitizer content could be varied over a wide range (0.025 – 0.49 wt%), while the DPA content was kept fixed at 37 wt% (Table 2). Since the only difference is the sub-percent content of PdmPH₃PMA in terpolymer **A1**, these polymers can be assumed to be completely miscible, and indeed the resulting blends **B2-B5** show a single T_g that is similar to the one of the poly(DPAMA-*co*-MMA) copolymer (134 °C).²² Thin films of **Series B** were prepared by the same solution-casting process that has been applied for the **series A** (Table 2, Figure 8). Since all chromophores were tethered to the polymer, and the polymers have similar composition no macroscopic phase-separation was observed and all blends displayed excellent transparency (Figure 8(a)). The films of **Series B** show similar absorption and fluorescence behavior as the materials from **Series A** (Figure S30, Figure 9). All films of **Series B** exhibited detectable green-to-blue upconversion upon excitation at 532 nm with a Nd:YAG green laser (2.5 mW, 208 mW/cm²). The fluorescence of DPA was also quenched by increase of PdmPH₃P content in **series B**, decrease of the UC was again observed with increase of PdmPH₃P content (Figure 8(b) and Figure 9). Similarly to the **Series A**, a significant phosphorescence was observed for the film **B2**, the latter was split

also into two distinct emission bands. Interestingly, when polymer **A1** was re-measured after about a month, a significant amount of additional phosphorescence was seen (Figures 5 and 9), which is indicative of sample aging and growth of PdmPH₃P aggregates over time. However, for freshly prepared samples, the lowest energy band was absent in samples with lower porphyrin content (films **B3-B5**) unlike their analogous freshly prepared terpolymer (films **A3-A5**). This result shows that porphyrin concentration is not the sole parameter governing stack formation but rather that the molecular architecture also plays a critical role. Interestingly, despite full phosphorescence quenching for blends containing less than 0.24 wt% of PdmPH₃P, the UC emission intensity kept increasing as the sensitizer concentration was diminished. Since PdmPH₃P molecules are homogeneously distributed along the polymer chains in **Series A** compared to **Series B**, one could postulate that the intermolecular stacking of PdmPH₃P molecules is more probable than between the PdmPH₃P units on the same chain (intra-molecular). This conjecture may also account for the overall lower upconversion emission intensity of **Series A** compared to **Series B** (Figure 10). Nevertheless, the absence of sharp melting peaks in the DSC thermograms indicates that these red-shifted peaks are most likely the result of minute aggregates (Figure S18-S22). Despite a significant amount of sample-to-sample variation, the comparison between the blends and terpolymers series suggests that the aggregation and composition of sensitizer in such materials represent a significant issue that needs to be further investigated.

CONCLUSIONS

A new series of terpolymers containing pendant emitter and sensitizer moieties was synthesized and enabled studies on the processes at play in upconverting glassy materials. The sensitizer composition was controlled either through the feed ratio during polymerization or by blending

a terpolymer with polyemitter. Unexpectedly, despite the covalent attachment, higher sensitizer contents did not equate to better upconversion. Instead, a considerable decrease of both sensitizer fluorescence quantum yield and delayed fluorescence intensity was observed. The results indicate that the decay of upconverted emission was due to the formation of non-radiative dye complexes, either in the form of ground-state aggregates or exciplexes, in addition to reabsorption of the emitted light due to the significant overlap of the absorption and emission spectra of the sensitizer and emitter. While similar trends had been observed in previous studies that focused on blends of PMMA and a similar sensitizer/emitter pair, as well as in blends of DPAMA copolymers with a metalloporphyrin sensitizer, the ultimate reason for this effect was unclear and thought to be related to sensitizer aggregation. The present studies shows strikingly that the main underlying problem is not the aggregation of the sensitizer, although this effect certainly is a contributor to undesired relaxation processes, even in the present terpolymers, but that electronic interactions between sensitizer and emitter are to blame. One way to circumvent this issue could potentially be the isolation of emitter and sensitizers in segregated domains to avoid cross-talking.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation (200021_13540/1 and R'equip 206021_128728) and the Adolphe Merkle Foundation.

REFERENCES AND NOTES

1. Y. C. Simon, C. Weder. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2012**, *22*, 20817-20830.
2. J. Z. Zhao, S. M. Ji, H. M. Guo. *Rsc Adv* **2011**, *1*, 937-950.
3. K. H. Naqvi. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1968**, *1*, 561-562.
4. C. A. Parker. *Tr. Faraday Soc.* **1964**, *60*, 1998-2008.
5. C. A. Parker, C. G. Hatchard. *P. Chem. Soc. London* **1962**, 386-387.
6. S. A. Bagnich, H. Bässler. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2003**, *381*, 464-470.
7. P. E. Keivanidis, S. Balushev, T. Miteva, G. Nelles, U. Scherf, A. Yasuda, G. Wegner. *Adv. Mater.* **2003**, *15*, 2095-2098.
8. R. R. Islangulov, J. Lott, C. Weder, F. N. Castellano. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2007**, *129*, 12652-12653.
9. C. Weder, T. N. Singh-Rachford, J. Lott, F. N. Castellano. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 12007-12014.
10. Y. C. Simon, S. Bai, M. K. Sing, H. Dietsch, M. Achermann, C. Weder. *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2012**, *33*, 498-502.
11. Y. C. Simon, C. Weder. *Chimia* **2012**, *66*, 878-878.
12. K. Sripathy, R. W. MacQueen, J. R. Peterson, Y. Y. Cheng, M. Dvorak, D. R. McCamey, N. D. Treat, N. Stingelin, T. W. Schmidt. *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2015**, *3*, 616-622.
13. R. Vadrucci, C. Weder, Y. C. Simon. *Materials Horizons* **2015**, *2*, 120-124.
14. A. Monguzzi, M. Frigoli, C. Larpent, R. Tubino, F. Meinardi. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2012**, *22*, 139-143.
15. A. Monguzzi, R. Tubino, S. Hoseinkhani, M. Campione, F. Meinardi. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2012**, *14*, 4322-4332.
16. P. B. Merkel, J. P. Dinnocenzo. *J. Lumin.* **2009**, *129*, 303-306.
17. J. P. Dinnocenzo, L. Feffar, M. Mis, S. Farid, P. B. Merkel, D. R. Robello. *J. Org. Chem.* **2008**, *73*, 5683-5692.
18. F. Marsico, A. Turshatov, R. Peköz, Y. Avlasevich, M. Wagner, K. Weber, D. Donadio, K. Landfester, S. Balushev, F. R. Wurm. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 11057-11064.
19. S.-H. Lee, Á. Sonseca, R. Vadrucci, E. Giménez, E. J. Foster, Y. Simon. *J. Inorg. Organomet. Polym. Mat.* **2014**, *24*, 898-903.

20. S. H. Lee, J. R. Lott, Y. C. Simon, C. Weder. *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2013**, *1*, 5142-5148.
21. R. Vadrucci, C. Weder, Y. C. Simon. *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2014**, *2*, 2837-2841.
22. S. H. Lee, M. A. Ayer, R. Vadrucci, C. Weder, Y. C. Simon. *Polym. Chem.* **2014**, *5*, 6898-6904.
23. A. Monguzzi, R. Tubino, F. Meinardi. *Phys. Rev. B* **2008**, *77*, 155122-155121-155124.
24. S. Balushev, J. Jacob, Y. S. Avlasevich, P. E. Keivanidis, T. Miteva, A. Yasuda, G. Nelles, A. C. Grimsdale, K. Müllen, G. Wegner. *ChemPhysChem* **2005**, *6*, 1250-1253.
25. A. J. Tilley, M. J. Kim, M. Chen, K. P. Ghiggino. *Polymer* **2013**, *54*, 2865-2872.
26. A. J. Tilley, B. E. Robotham, R. P. Steer, K. P. Ghiggino. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2015**, *618*, 198-202.
27. X. Yu, X. Cao, X. Chen, N. Ayres, P. Zhang. *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51*, 588-591.
28. P. Rothmund. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1935**, *57*, 2010-2011.
29. L. R. Milgrom. *Nature* **1997**, *390*, 136-136.
30. S. Shanmugathan, C. K. Johnson, C. Edwards, E. K. Matthews, D. Dolphin, R. W. Boyle. *J. Porphyrins Phthalocyanines* **2000**, *4*, 228-232.
31. S. Shanmugathan, C. Edwards, R. W. Boyle. *Tetrahedron* **2000**, *56*, 1025-1046.
32. V. Rozhkov, D. Wilson, S. Vinogradov. *Macromolecules* **2002**, *35*, 1991-1993.
33. T. Serevicius, R. Komskis, P. Adomenas, O. Adomeniene, V. Jankauskas, A. Gruodis, K. Kazlauskas, S. Jursenas. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2014**, *16*, 7089-7101.
34. V. N. Knyukshto, A. M. Shul'ga, E. I. Sagun, E. I. Zen'kevich. *Opt. Spectrosc.* **2006**, *100*, 590-601.
35. J. W. Buchler, C. Dreher, F. M. Kunzel. *Struct Bond* **1995**, *84*, 1-69.
36. J. A. Shelnut, X. Z. Song, J. G. Ma, S. L. Jia, W. Jentzen, C. J. Medforth. *Chem Soc Rev* **1998**, *27*, 31-41.
37. M. O. Senge, C. J. Medforth, T. P. Forsyth, D. A. Lee, M. M. Olmstead, W. Jentzen, R. K. Pandey, J. A. Shelnut, K. M. Smith. *Inorg. Chem.* **1997**, *36*, 1149-1163.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Soo Hyon Lee, David C. Thévenaz, Christoph Weder*, and Yoan C. Simon*

Glassy Poly(methacrylate) Polymers with Covalently Attached Emitters and Sensitizers for Low-Power Light Upconversion

A new series of light-upconverting terpolymers in which a sensitizer/emitter is reported, where the chromophore pair is covalently attached to a poly(methacrylate) backbone. A surprising relation between the polymers' composition and ability to upconvert green into blue light is found and explained.

FIGURE 1. Normalized absorbance (dotted lines) and emission (solid lines) spectra of solutions of PdmPH3PMA (10 μ M) and DPAMA (0.2 mM) in toluene. The emission spectra of DPAMA and PdmPH3PMA were recorded upon excitation at 375 nm and at 532 nm, respectively. The upconverted fluorescence emission spectrum of a solution of DPAMA (22 mM) and PdmPH3PMA (0.5 mM) in toluene was recorded upon excitation at 532 nm with a 2.5 mW Nd:YAG laser.

FIGURE 2. Emission spectra of the terpolymer poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MMA-*stat*-PdmPH3PMA) (Sample **A1**) in toluene solution (2.48 mg / 5 mL) and in the solid state. (a) Upconverted delayed fluorescence of the polymer solution (red, solid) and the mixture of the two monomers (blue, solid) as shown in Figure 1 (blue, solid). (b) Direct emission (fluorescence) of the DPA moieties in the copolymer solution (green, dashed) and in a 80 μ m thin solution-cast film (blue, dashed) recorded upon excitation at 375 nm with a Xe arc lamp. Upconverted delayed fluorescence of the solution (red, solid) and the solution-cast film (purple, solid) were recorded by excitation at 532 nm with a Nd:YAG laser (208 mW/cm²). The intensities are arbitrarily adjusted to optimally fit the graph and permit comparison of the spectral shape.

FIGURE 3. (a) Picture of solution-cast films of terpolymer **Series A**. All samples have a thickness of *ca.* 80 μm , comprise 30-37 wt% of DPA and PdmPH₃P in the following concentration: (from left) 0.73, 0.11, 0.05, 0.045, and 0.012 wt%. (b) Picture of the same samples as in (a) taken under illumination with a 365 nm UV lamp.

FIGURE 4. (a) Absorption spectra of solution-cast films of terpolymer **Series A** as function PdmPH₃P content. The films had a thickness of *ca.* 80 μm . (b) Emission intensity (integrated between 400 and 510 nm) of the same samples. The samples were excited at 375 nm.

FIGURE 5. Upconverted emission intensity (425-500 nm) and phosphorescence (620-800 nm) of films of **Series A**. All spectra were acquired upon excitation with Nd:YAG laser at 532 nm. The X-axis was cut to remove the excitation peak.

FIGURE 6. Picture of the TTA-UC process in a film of **A5** comprising 0.012 wt% of PdmPH₃P and 31 wt% of DPA prepared by melt-processing at 150 °C upon excitation with a Nd:YAG laser at 532 nm (208 mW/cm²). The blue fluorescence in the center of the film originates from TTA-UC and was viewed through a 500 nm short-pass filter. The green spots are reflected incident light from the laser. The film was melt-processed in order to obtain a thicker self-standing film.

FIGURE 7. (a) Upconverted emission spectra of solution-cast films of terpolymer **A1** upon excitation with a laser at 532 nm at different excitation power densities as indicated in the graph. (b) Double logarithmic plot of the data shown in (a), and a least square fit of the data (slope = 1.45).

FIGURE 8. (a) Picture of solution-cast films of terpolymer **A1** (left) and blends of **A1** and a poly(DPAMA-co-MMA) copolymer (blends **B2-B5**). All samples comprise ca. 37 wt% DPA and 0.73, 0.49, 0.24, 0.12, and 0.025 wt% PdmPH₃P (from left to right). (b) Picture of the same samples as in (a) taken under illumination with a 365 nm UV lamp.

FIGURE 9. (a) Upconversion emission intensity (425-500 nm) and phosphorescence (620-800 nm) of films of **Series B**. All spectra were acquired upon excitation with Nd:YAG laser at 532 nm. The X-axis was cut to remove the excitation peak. b) Expansion of the region showing upconverted emission plotted in (a).

FIGURE 10. Variation of TTA-UC fluorescence intensity of **Series A** and **B** as a function of PdmPH₃P content normalized to the absorbance at 532 nm. The UC fluorescence of both series was recorded between 400-520 nm upon excitation at 532 nm with a green laser (2.5 mW, 208 mW/cm²).

SCHEMES:

SCHEME 1. Synthesis of the porphyrin-containing methacrylate monomer (PdmPH₃PMA).

SCHEME 2. Synthetic scheme of the polymerization of poly(DPAMA-*stat*-MMA-*stat*-PdmPH₃PMA).

TABLES:

TABLE 1. Characterization of terpolymers **Series A** made by free radical polymerization comprising PdmPH₃PMA:DPAMA and of the copolymer poly(DPAMA-co-MMA).

Polymer	Composition				Molecular weight		Yield %
	PdmPH ₃ PMA:DPAMA:MM A Feed (eq)	PdmPH ₃ PMA:DPAMA:MMA in copolymer(eq:eq:eq) ^{a,b}	DPA content ^{a)} (wt%)	PdmPH ₃ P content ^{b)} (wt%)	M _n ^{c)} (g/mol)	D ^{c)}	
DPAMA Copolymer^{d)}	0:1:5	0:1:4	37	0	110 000	1.9	66
A1	1:130:650	1:123:528	37	0.73	136 000	1.9	49
A2	1:200:1000	1:749:3958	34	0.11	145 000	2.7	37
A3	1:1000:5000	1:1745:8057	36	0.05	450 000	2.6	41
A4	1:1000:5000	1:1616:10423	30	0.045	120 000	1.7	51
A5	1:4000:20000	1:6262:38193	31	0.012	134 000	1.9	32

^{a)} The DPAMA:MMA ratio in the copolymer and terpolymers was determined via ¹H NMR spectroscopy by comparing the integrals of the benzylic protons of DPAMA at $\delta = 4.0$ ppm with the ester protons of both DPAMA and MMA at $\delta = 3.5$ ppm; the DPA weight content was then calculated from the DPAMA/MMA ratio. ^{b)} The PdmPH₃P content of the terpolymers was determined by absorption spectroscopy using the extinction coefficient of PdmPH₃PMA ($\epsilon = 29\,560$ L/mol/cm at 530 nm in THF). ^{c)} The number-average molecular weight (M_n) and the molar mass dispersity (D) of the copolymer and terpolymers were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) in THF (Figure S12-S16). ^{d)} Taken from ref. ²².

TABLE 2. Composition of the copolymer blend **Series B** prepared by solution casting mixtures of the terpolymer **A1** and the copolymer poly(DPAMA-co-MMA). The DPA and PdmPH₃P content were calculated from the mixing ratio and the compositions of the two polymers (Table 1).

Polymer Blend	Composition		
	Terpolymer A1 /poly(DPAMA-co- MMA) (wt%/wt%)	DPA content (wt%)	PdmPH ₃ P content (wt%)
A1	1/0	37	0.73
B2	2/1	37	0.49
B3	1/2	37	0.24
B4	1/5	37	0.12
B5	1/29	37	0.025